

Effect of urea applied with neem cake on disease intensity and insect population in ricefields

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We compared blast (B1) and brown leaf spot (BLS) incidence and green leafhopper (GLH) and brown planthopper (BPH) populations in farmers' fields where urea with and without neem cake was applied with and without insecticides in two seasons, Sep 1989-Mar 1990.

Rice variety ADT39 was fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. Half the N and all the PK were applied as basal; the remaining N was split-applied during tillering and panicle initiation. Neem cake (20%) was mixed with urea at a 1.5 ratio for all N applications. Monocroto-

Effect of urea with neem cake on disease intensity and insect population of rice. ^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1989-90.

Treatment	Disease intensity (%)		Insect population (no./hill)		Yield (t/ha)	Additional cost ^b (\$)	Additional benefit ^b (%)	Benefit: cost
	B1	BLS	GLH	BPH				
Urea + neem cake + pesticides	8.2 a	13.1 a	6.2 a	16.3 a	5.8 a	12.9	84.0	6.51
Urea + pesticides	8.3 a	14.6 a	7.4 a	18.2 a	5.7 a	8.2	51.6	6.29
Urea + neem cake	18.7 b	23.8 b	23.8 b	24.8 b	5.6 ab	4.8	29.9	6.23
Urea alone (control)	20.1 b	34.2 c	34.2 c	42.5 c	5.4 b			

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^b Cost and benefit were converted to US dollars from Indian rupees.

phos and edifenphos were sprayed at panicle initiation.

B1, BLS, GLH, and BPH incidence was measured 15 d after panicle initiation (10 sited/0.40 ha). Data from both seasons (Sep-Dec and Dec-Mar) were pooled.

Applying neem cake with urea was no more effective against diseases and insects than pesticide application (see table). But it significantly reduced BLS

intensity and GLH and BPH populations compared with control. Neem cake + pesticide gave higher yields than the other treatments.

The benefit:cost ratio of all treatments was about 6.0. Neem cake can be recommended to minimize disease and insect problems and reduce N loss in rice. In epidemic areas, pesticides can be used to check pests rapidly. ■

Efficacy of fungicides against enzyme produced by rice sheath blight (ShB) pathogen

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The pathogenic mechanism of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, which incites rice ShB disease, is complex, varied, and inadequately explored. The activity of enzyme tools of the pathogens for causing diseases, however, is known to be affected by different chemicals, including fungicides.

Of the fungicides that have been tested, carbendazim (systemic) was most effective in reducing mycelial growth, production and germination of sclerotia, and lesion length. We studied the effect of this fungicide on the activity of enzymes of *R. solani*.

Three enzymes—cellulase (Cx), polygalacturonase (endo PG), and protease—were produced in Richard's solution containing 0.5% carboxyl methyl cellulase (CMC) or 0.05% sodium

polypectate as a C source, or 1% casein as a N source. A stock solution of carbendazim (100% active ingredient basis) was prepared in buffer solution at experimental pH levels.

Efficacy was determined by viscosimetric method (Fenske-Ostwald's Viscometer, size-300). Components of the reaction mixture were poured into the large arm of the viscometer at appropriate rates: 1.2% CMC for cellulase, or 1.2% sodium polypectate for PG, or 1% casein for protease; buffer (acetate at pH 5.2 for cellulase and endo PG, or acetate at pH 7.0 for protease); carbendazim, distilled water, and the enzyme source prepared from 8-d-old cultures. Carbendazim from stock solution was added to the viscometer placed vertically in a water bath at 30 °C to give concentrations of 25, 50, and 100 µg/ml. The quantity of the remaining chemicals was substrate 5 ml, buffer 2 ml, and enzyme source 1 ml. Final volume was adjusted to 10 ml by adding distilled water. The efflux time of the reaction mixture for 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 min was recorded. Autoclaved enzyme was used as control.

Carbendazim significantly reduced the activity of endo PG. Loss in viscosity of

sodium polypectate for 20, 40, 60, and 80 min was 18.5, 24.8, 25.9, and 26.1%, respectively, at 100 µg carbendazim/ml. Maximum inhibition in Cx activity was 16.6, 39.1, and 49.5% at 25, 50, and 100 µg carbendazim/ml, respectively. At all concentrations, carbendazim was effective in inhibiting loss in viscosity of casein. The inhibition of the pectic enzyme (PG) might be due to pectate binding properties; protease activity might be disturbed because the conformation in amino acid sequences might be affected.

The fungicides that affect disease development might be doing so by hindering the activity of the enzymes essential in pathological manifestations induced by biotic agents. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.